

Comparative Analysis of Chat GPT, Chatbots, and Google Bard: Insights and Implications for Advancing AI Research

Biswarup Yogi¹, Souvik Maitra², Avirup Dutta³, Avijit Bera⁴, Debarshi Bandyopadhyay⁵

¹ Brainware University, Computational Sciences, Kolkata, India

² Brainware University, Computational Sciences, Kolkata, India

³ Brainware University, Computational Sciences, Kolkata, India

⁴ Brainware University, Computational Sciences, Kolkata, India

⁵ Brainware University, Computational Sciences, Kolkata, India

Abstract— In today's world, people are really interested in Artificial Intelligence (AI) because it's so advanced and fascinating. Scientists and researchers study AI using specific goals and methods. One of the most exciting developments in AI is something called Chat GPT. When it first came out, it got a lot of attention because it was so innovative. This paper is like a big study that looks at Chat GPT in detail. Chat GPT, Google Gemini AI (formerly known as Google Bard AI), and chatbots are the main topics of discussion. The main goal is to tell people about what experts think of these things. By comparing them, the paper helps us understand their strengths and weaknesses better. By sharing all this information, the paper helps us learn more about Chat GPT, AI based chatbots, and Google's own Gemini AI. This helps researchers keep moving forward and discovering new things in the world of AI.

Keywords— Artificial Intelligence (AI), Chat GPT, Google Gemini AI, AI-based Chatbots

I. INTRODUCTION

We decided to work on this project because after Open AI released Chat GPT, there was a lot of talk about how it might affect cybersecurity. We were curious about how Chat GPT works, so we wanted to learn more about it. We also wanted to explore other talking computer programs like Google's Gemini AI. To write this article, we looked at many academic papers about AI Chatbots, the very popular Chat GPT and Google Gemini AI. We also read some news articles about Google Bard AI. We found information from websites like Wikipedia and ResearchGate too. Literature Review is done in the second part of our paper. Here, we talk about different studies and projects related to Chatbots, Google Gemini AI and Chat GPT. Starting from section 3, we talk about chatbots. We cover their history, types, how they're made, and how they're used. In section 4, we focus on Chat GPT. We describe its nature, operation, applications, users, and restrictions. Then, in section 5, we discuss Google Gemini AI and what it can do. Finally, in section 6, we compare Chat GPT and Google Gemini AI briefly.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been some big improvements in how computers understand and use language, thanks to things like Natural Language Processing (NLP), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Neural Networks. One big thing that's come out of this is something called GPT VER-2 and GPT VER-3, which are like really smart computer programs. They can answer questions, write text, and understand language. But these programs aren't perfect. Sometimes they can have biases or make mistakes. To fix this, people have come up with interactive versions like Chat GPT. This is a better version of GPT VER-2 and GPT VER-3 that you can talk to. Lots of researchers have looked into how Chat GPT can be used in different areas. For example, Rohit Tamrakar & Niraj Wani studied how to make a new kind of chatbot. They showed how chatbots can be useful in many situations, like in real-life applications.

Similarly, Brady D. Lund and Ting Wang[1] explored different things about Chat GPT, like where it came from and how it works. They also looked into how it could be used, such as in writing academic papers. After talking about Chat GPT, the next thing we're looking at is Google Bard AI. This is a new thing from Google, but there's not a lot of information about it yet. One study by Bal Ram and Pratima

Verma in 2023[2] looked at Google Bard AI(now Gemini AI) in detail, comparing it to Chat GPT and seeing how it could be used.

Below, there's a table that shows some of the research that's been done on these topics.

Sl No	Author	Year	Proposed work
1	Mgr. Tomáš ZEMČÍK [3]	2019	reviewed the development, functions and history of chatbots
2	Hendrik Kempt [4]	2020	Chatbots and the Domestication of AI
3	Nataliya Mutovkina [5]	2021	Utilizing Chatbots to Enhance the Educational Experience
4	Mingyu Zong, Bhaskar, Krishnamachari [6]	2022	A brief history of the GPT3 and some of its key components
5	Md. Saidur Rahaman,M. M. Tahmid Ahsan,Nishath Anjum [7]	2023	Chat GPT & Google Gemini AI
6	Intiaz Ahmed, Mashrafi Kajol, Uzma Hasan, Partha Protim Datta, Ayon Roy [8]	2024	A short comparison between Chat GPT and Google Gemini AI

III.INTRODUCTION OF CHATBOTS

A chatbot is a clever computer programme built with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). It can communicate with individuals either by typing or speech. When you converse to a chatbot, it listens to what you say or type and responds with intelligent and useful responses. Chatbots are designed to be available at all times, allowing you to communicate with them whenever needed. They employ Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Sentiment Analysis to comprehend and communicate with users via text or phone call. The customer care chat on Amazon and EVA from HDFC Bank are two examples of chatbots.[9], [10].

A. Historical background of Chatbots

The very first chatbot, ELIZA, was created by Joseph Weizenbowm in 1966 at an AI lab. ELIZA worked by recognizing certain words and then responding accordingly. Many chatbots today still use this same approach. After ELIZA came to PARRY, developed by therapist Kenneth Colby at Stanford University. Then, in 1995, a more advanced version of ELIZA called Alice Bot or ALICE was created. ALICE even competes in an annual AI contest called the Loebner Prize.

B. Types of Chatbots:

All-Purpose Chatbots: These chatbots can answer any question, no matter what it's about. For example, Chorus.[10]

Multi-Domain Chatbots: These chatbots work in more than one area or topic. For instance, AskWiz.[10]

Specific-Domain Chatbots: These chatbots only deal with questions or issues in a particular field. Like Snap Travel, which focuses on travel-related queries.[10]

C. Goals of Chatbots:

Informative Chatbots: These chatbots help users find specific information they're looking for. Like Guardian.[10]

Conversational Chatbots: These chatbots chat with users just like a real person would. Also, like Guardian [10].

Task-Oriented Chatbots: These chatbots are designed for specific tasks or jobs, such as booking rooms [10].

IV. CHAT GPT

Followed by a quick introduction to chatbots this section provides an in-depth analysis of Chat GPT, including its definition, operation, methods, applications, constraints, and more.

A. Introduction:

Chat GPT is a chatbot developed by Open AI, a research lab established in 2015. Open AI has been a trailblazer in artificial intelligence, offering technologies such as Chat GPT and DALL-E. Text responses generated by the GPT language model closely resemble human language. Chat GPT is based on the GPT VER-3 architecture, which is excellent at creating natural-sounding text. Previous versions, such as GPT VER-1 and GPT VER-2, existed before GPT VER-3. Following its introduction in June 2018, GPT VER-1 generated comments that were grammatically accurate but often repeated. More diverse, GPT VER-2 was initially barred from its entire model due to potential abuse, but it was made available in February 2019 [1].

B. Features and Functionality:

A prototype of Chat GPT has been released by OpenAI, which understands language and provides responses. Experts believe it's an advanced Chatbot that could even rival Google. It's crucial to remember that while Chat GPT is based on the GPT language model, it cannot identify voice. It can write articles, essays, code, and respond to queries, among other things. It processes user input and generates responses that closely resemble human language. Chat GPT represents a significant innovation in Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, and Natural Language Processing [1].

C. Applications of Chat GPT:

We'll move on to discussing Chat GPT's real-world applications once we've gained a clear understanding of the platform, including its multiple facets and approach. We have discussed Chat GPT's numerous uses and benefits for various user groups in this section.

The applications span across a spectrum of fields such as science, philosophy, and writing, among others. Chat GPT exhibits an extensive array of applications across nearly all domains, elaborated as follows:

- Questioning-Answering: Chat GPT can provide support for a wide range of inquiries posed by users, whether they pertain to academic subjects, the medical realm, technology, mathematical quandaries, customer service, and more [6], [14].
- Facilitating creative endeavours: Chat GPT can play a role in aiding various creative projects such as composing news headlines, crafting poetry, drafting essays, and generating articles [6], [14].
- Contribution to coding and debugging processes: The tool may help you create code snippets, programming scripts, and spot issues in the code. Empirical investigations have shown that 38 of the 80 programmes developed by Chat GPT are of commendable quality. It can also produce code in a number of computer languages, including Python and C++, based on natural language input. Furthermore, it can debug, provide suggestions, and auto-complete code segments by leveraging its knowledge of APIs and many programming languages.[6], [14].
- Enriching math tutoring experiences: Many students encounter challenges in resolving doubts related to their mathematical or scientific queries, a gap that Chat GPT can swiftly address [6], [14].

- Language translation: With exposure to a huge number of languages and processing approximately 500 billion words, Chat GPT possesses extensive linguistic knowledge enabling it to translate various forms of text from one language to another [6], [14].
- Text classification and sentiment analysis: Chat GPT can categorize different forms of text such as articles, blogs, etc., into distinct groupings like authentic/spam, genuine/fake, and more [6], [14].
- Writing assistance: The tool can aid in the creation of authentic content like essays, poems, articles, stories, and summaries, facilitating tasks such as condensing lengthy texts into concise forms [6], [14].
- Development of Chatbots: Notably, Chat GPT can be leveraged to build novel Chatbots capable of engaging in conversations [6], [14].
- Geophysics applications: Chat GPT can contribute to resolving geophysics-related issues [6], [14].
- Medical field applications: The tool can generate various medical documents and reports beneficial for healthcare professionals, offer support to doctors by furnishing pertinent information for clinical decisions, aid in drug discovery through virtual screening, and function as a virtual medical assistant for patients by analyzing and providing insights on symptoms, medications, treatments, etc. (referred to as medical Chatbots [6], [14].
- Utilization in the realm of social sciences: The tool is capable of conducting data analysis and producing reports across a range of social science disciplines such as economics, sociology, and more. Its application extends to market research through the examination of diverse market trends and consumer requirements. Furthermore, it is capable of doing political analysis by examining various political trends, surveys, and related data. [2].
- Practical implementation in philosophy: It is capable of formulating a variety of arguments within philosophical debates. Additionally, it can conceptualise and visualise a wide range of philosophical theories and notions. [2].
- Usage in the domain of financial sciences: The tool is adept at conducting various forms of analysis within the financial sector. Moreover, it is equipped to provide investment guidance and detect instances of fraud [2].

D. Usage of Chat GPT based on users

After elucidating the various applications of Chat GPT, the utilization of Chatbots has been delineated for diverse groups such as students, educators, healthcare professionals, etc. For students, Chat GPT proves beneficial in tasks like solving math/science problems, composing essays, completing homework, and more. In the case of teachers, it can aid in addressing queries, enhancing knowledge, and improving teaching proficiency, among other uses. In the medical domain, Chat GPT can contribute to creating medical documents, and reports, providing valuable information, and functioning as a virtual medical aide. Engineers can benefit from Chat GPT for coding, debugging, problem-solving, research insights, project development support, and similar tasks. Politicians can utilize it for devising strategies, conducting political surveys, acquiring political insights, and supporting ministerial/legislative activities. Administrators and government officials can leverage Chat GPT to comprehend public issues, facilitate administrative processes, and more. Legal professionals like lawyers and judges can seek assistance from Chat GPT to enhance their understanding of legal provisions, access case records/judgments, and so forth. Farmers can utilise Chat GPT for insights on crops, weather forecasts, government policies, and related information. Businesspersons may benefit from Chat GPT by receiving guidance on business strategies, accessing data/analytics, understanding product varieties, and more. Writers and poets can enhance their creativity, and explore various literary works, editorials, and historical writings on diverse subjects, among other uses. Journalists can utilize Chat GPT to gather information, enhance writing skills, and support journalistic endeavours.

Limitations and challenges of Chat GPT While Chatbots exhibit a broad spectrum of real-world applications, they also present several limitations and challenges for different user segments, as outlined below:

- The data limitation is evident in the information provided, indicating that Chat GPT's data encompasses only up to the year 2021, rendering data beyond that year unavailable.
- Bias is inherent in every individual globally, transcending into the machines they develop, including Chat GPT. Allegations have surfaced regarding its racial bias, indicating a tendency to favour white individuals and depict them as superior, juxtaposed with a negative portrayal of black individuals. Furthermore, Chat GPT has come under fire for its gender biases, which present women as sensitive and focused on their families and men as powerful and masculine. Claims have also emerged linking Muslims with terrorism and violence in association with Chat GPT [6], [14].
- In our experimentation with Chat GPT, it became apparent that its solutions to mathematical and physics problems are not consistently accurate. Furthermore, due to its reliance on text inputs, there are instances where it struggles to precisely interpret and identify errors in the code [6].
- Despite possessing extensive knowledge across various domains like science, mathematics, and engineering, Chat GPT's understanding of syntax and semantics is constrained, leading to frequent inaccuracies in its responses [6].
- The management of vast amounts of data by Chat GPT raises significant concerns regarding privacy and security, particularly impacting entities like corporations and national defence that handle sensitive information[6].
- Despite extensive training, Chat GPT lacks the common sense exhibited by humans [2].
- The design limitations of Chat GPT restrict its ability to tackle complex problems in high-standard and NLP domains [14].
- Due of its extensive expertise in a variety of industries, Chat GPT can be abused by terrorist groups, criminal enterprises, and hostile countries. Additionally, it can be exploited by fraudulent entities for activities like spreading spam messages and organizing scams [14].
- The advancement of artificial creativity facilitated by Chat GPT may have adverse implications on human creativity [14].
- While Chat GPT can offer substantial assistance to students, it also poses risks to their academic journey. Students may resort to using shortcuts provided by Chat GPT to swiftly solve homework, mathematical problems, and creative tasks, potentially stifling their innate problem-solving skills, creativity, and learning aptitude.

V. GOOGLE GEMINI AI

Google announced Google Gemini AI, formerly known as Google Bard AI, on February 7, 2023. It is similar to Chat GPT. One of Google Gemini AI's primary functions is conversational interaction with people, which is a feature that it shares with Chat GPT. Google Gemini AI, powered by LaMDA (Language Model for Dialogue Applications) is thought to have been launched by Google to compete with Chat GPT, which quickly surpassed 100 million users in just two months after becoming live. Although not available to the general public, Google Gemini is accessible to "trusted testers."

Sundar Pichai, the CEO of Google, has emphasized that its launch aims to enhance the efficiency, intelligence, specialization, and utility of the search engine. [2], [11], [15].

Some distinctive characteristics of Google Gemini AI are worth mentioning.

First off, Google Gemini AI has the capacity to combine intelligence, power, and creativity [2].

Secondly, it will include a feedback mechanism allowing it to receive user feedback and enhance its performance accordingly. Moreover, Google Gemini AI will incorporate the most up-to-date data [11].

Lastly, Google Gemini AI avoids making inferences or passing judgments/comments based on presumptions [7].

VI. BRIEF COMPARISON BETWEEN CHAT GPT AND GOOGLE GEMINI AI

After debating on the fundamental introduction, basic features, and other aspects of Chatbots, namely Chat GPT and Google Gemini AI, a succinct comparison was done between the two Chatbots.

Comparison between Chat GPT and Google Gemini AI:

- Chat GPT contains data up to the year 2021, while Google Gemini AI continuously updates its data repository [11].
- Chat GPT necessitates scouring through various documents to gather information, whereas Google Gemini can swiftly retrieve information from the web [11].
- Limitations of Chat GPT include potential biases and the dissemination of inaccurate information, shortcomings that are largely mitigated by Google Gemini AI [11].
- Google Gemini AI offers more detailed and elaborated information compared to Chat GPT [11].
- Chat GPT, a text-based Chatbot, responds exclusively in textual form, whereas Google Gemini is designed for universal comprehension, even by children [11].
- Chat GPT, an NLP system based on neural networks, excels in efficiency and precision, while Google Gemini AI is tailored for conversational interfaces [12].
- Chat GPT is capable of generating text in a wider array of contexts than Google Gemini AI [12].
- Google Gemini AI exhibits rapid environmental responsiveness, setting it apart from Chat GPT [12].
- Chat GPT has 175 billion parameters, but Google Gemini AI has 1.37 billion parameters and a vocabulary of over 1.5 trillion words. Chat GPT, however, has the benefit of having a large vocabulary [12].
- Chat GPT offers plagiarism detection functionality, a feature absent in Google Gemini AI [13].
- In comparison to Google Gemini AI, Chat GPT demonstrates superior responsiveness in handling customer inquiries in FAQ format [13].
- The core edition of Chat GPT Plus costs \$20 per month, whereas Google Gemini AI is free of charge. [13]

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this article, we looked at the history of chatbots, how they are created, the many forms, and more. We next examined the characteristics of Chat GPT and Google Gemini AI, followed by a quick comparison of the two. Based on our investigation, we conclude that, while both AI-powered Chatbots are valuable in today's environment, they also have limits that must be addressed in the future.

Chat GPT received a lot of attention when it first came out, despite some flaws we discussed earlier. Because it's built on AI and ML, we expect it to keep improving. 1)Future improvements might include better accuracy and responses, as it gathers more data over time. 2)There's also excitement about Chat GPT working alongside new technologies like virtual and augmented reality, which could open up new possibilities across different fields. 3)Dealing with issues like bias and mistakes is crucial for Chat GPT's development. This means it needs thorough training with diverse data to fix these issues.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lund, Brady D., and Ting Wang. "Chatting about ChatGPT: how may AI and GPT impact academia and libraries?." *Library hi tech news* 40, no. 3 (2023): 26-29.
- [2] Ram, Bal, and Pratima Verma. "Artificial intelligence AI-based Chatbot study of ChatGPT, Google AI Bard and Baidu AI." *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences* 8, no. 01 (2023): 258-261.
- [3] Zemčík, M. Tmáš. "A brief history of chatbots." *DEStech Transactions on Computer Science and Engineering* 10 (2019).
- [4] Kempt, Hendrik. *Chatbots and the domestication of AI: a relational approach*. Springer Nature, 2020.
- [5] Mutovkina, Nataliya. "Chatbots as a tool to optimize the educational process." In *Advances in Artificial Systems for Power Engineering*, pp. 15-25. Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- [6] Zong, Mingyu, and Bhaskar Krishnamachari. "A survey on GPT-3." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.00857* (2022).
- [7] Rahaman, Md Saidur, MM Tahmid Ahsan, Nishath Anjum, Harold Jan R. Terano, and Md Mizanur Rahman. "From ChatGPT-3 to GPT-4: a significant advancement in ai-driven NLP tools." *Journal of Engineering and Emerging Technologies* 2, no. 1 (2023): 1-11.
- [8] Ahmed, Imtiaz, Mashrafi Kajol, Uzma Hasan, Partha Protim Datta, Ayon Roy, and Md Rokonzaman Reza. "ChatGPT versus Bard: A comparative study." *Engineering Reports* (2024): e12890.
- [9] Tamrakar, Rohit, and Niraj Wani. "Design and development of CHATBOT: A review." *ResearchGate*, Apr (2021).
- [10] Adamopoulou, Eleni, and Lefteris Moussiades. "Chatbots: History, technology, and applications." *Machine Learning with applications* 2 (2020): 100006.
- [11] Jagran English. (2022, July 1). Google Bard vs ChatGPT: How Google is taking on OpenAI with its new software, key differences.
- [12] Md. S. Rahaman, M. M. T. Ahsan, N. Anjum, Md. Rahman, and Md. Rahman, "The AI Race is on! Google's Google Bard and Openai's Chatgpt Head to Head: An Opinion Article," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2023
- [13] Drew Robb, "Chat GPT vs Google Bard: Generative AI comparison" *eWEEK*, 22 March 2023.
- [14] P. Dell'Aversana, "GPT-3: a new cooperation scenario between humans and machines. Benefits and limitations of GPT-3 as a coding virtual assistant," 2023.
- [15] Dasgupta, "Google Bard vs Chatgpt, and the concerns with both AI chatbots," *Indian Express*, 27 August 2021.